

D1.6 Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) for assessment - I

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Executive Summary

This deliverable presents the main performance metrics for the evaluation of the Sharework system performances in a general manufacturing process. The performance metrics are defined in terms of impact in an industrial scenario and assessment of modules performances. All identified metrics are analysed in detail, providing details on why they are relevant, which dynamics of the process they can evaluate and how they can be measured. When relevant, interactions between different models are highlighted to provide a deeper overview on how outputs and metrics relative of a module can become the input and the basis for new metrics of another module.

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Terminology and Acronyms

<i>C2I</i>	<i>Command, Control and Intelligence</i>
<i>C4I</i>	<i>Command, Control, Communications, Computers and Intelligence</i>
<i>EC</i>	<i>European Commission</i>
<i>EU</i>	<i>European Union</i>
<i>FP</i>	<i>Framework Programme</i>
<i>PMB</i>	<i>Project Management Board</i>
<i>PMP</i>	<i>Project Management Plan</i>
<i>STAB</i>	<i>Scientific and Technical Advisory Board</i>
<i>WP</i>	<i>Work Package</i>
<i>UAS</i>	<i>Unmanned Aerial System</i>
<i>UGV</i>	<i>Unmanned Ground Vehicle</i>
<i>CPCS</i>	<i>Central Process Control System</i>
<i>NPS</i>	<i>Navigation and Perception Sensors</i>
<i>PMS</i>	<i>Process Monitoring Sensors</i>
<i>RU-V1</i>	<i>Robotic Unit Version 1</i>

1 Introduction

This document proposes and analyse the most relevant metrics to be used for the assessment of the Sharework system performances in industrial manufacturing environment. The work included in this Deliverable 1.6 is referred to the activities performed in task 1.5 of WP1.

The aim of D1.6 is to provide an overview of which performance indicators have a higher relevance for the description, validation and evaluation of the Sharework system as a whole, regardless of the specific use case. For this reason, performance metrics discussed in this document are not related to each of the four use cases selected in Sharework, but, on one side, analyse the implementation in a general manufacturing process and, on the other side, addresses the Sharework technological modules means for validation as independent modules and in connection with the other ones.

The KPIs for industrial impact evaluation have been selected following the four main drivers of the Sharework project, namely, Productivity, Safety, Cost and Human factors. For the modules KPIs, similar modules have been grouped to simplify the presentation of common basis for the performance metrics definition.

The more detailed KPIs, focused on the specific requirements and implementation specifications for the four Sharework use cases will be included in D1.7.

D1.6 and D1.7 will act as a basis for the System performance assessment and benchmarking activities that will be performed in task 7.4.

2 Structure and description of contents

Deliverable 1.6 is divided in four main sections.

In the first section, the state of the art on Key Performance Indicators definition and selection is briefly presented, with examples from literature, industrial standards for robotics and real industrial implementation.

In the second section, the KPIs for the evaluation of the Sharework system impact in an industrial manufacturing process are identified and detailed, describing their importance and how to measure and evaluate them. These KPIs have been selected following the four main drivers of the Sharework project, namely Productivity, Safety, Cost and Human-factors.

In the third section, performance metrics are justified and presented for each of the 14 technological modules of Sharework. A general introduction in terms of WPs is provided, in order to simplify the presentation of the common basis for modules that address similar issues and avoid repetitions.

The final section provides the conclusions of the deliverable and the next steps of specific KPIs definition.

3 State-of-the-art key performance indicators

The industrial processes are always developed and designed according to their macroscopic goals, which are based on the process typology (e.g., a product manufacturing process, or an industrial service), the field of application, and the main criticalities that are foreseen in the scenario.

An operational process may be constantly monitored in a unique way, in order to have a clear vision of what can be improved or optimized, and how to do it. During process development, several industrial standards and their sets of KPIs may have been applied, in order to measure, calculate or estimate the quality of each single process step.

More in general, KPIs are performance measures employed by management techniques to enable efficient and effective business monitoring, and are generally acknowledged to be a set of measures critical to the current and future success of any project.

When a KPI set has to be defined for a certain process, some basic “rules” have to be considered, in order to have a really useful tool to monitor and optimize it. In particular, the chosen KPIs should be quantifiable, accurate, and their meaning understood by everyone within the team contributing to the project. The measures should be calculated from data that can be readily collected without undue cost. Moreover, they should be measured frequently, reflecting current priorities. The measures should be relevant for the process and then support the strategic objectives of the project (e.g., the final product features or costs). Finally, they have to be consistent, which means that they should not conflict with other performance measures.

Features of the KPI set, such as their optimal number, has been widely analyzed in past studies. Kaplan and Norton¹, in their balanced scorecard approach, suggest less than 20 KPIs for an optimal set, while Parmenter about 10² and Hope and Fraser³ and Price Waterhouse Coopers⁴ suggest less than 10 KPIs.

The MESA (Manufacturing Enterprise Solutions Association) organization has sponsored research over the past years to help the manufacturing marketplace identify the most important metrics and help decision makers understand metrics improvements and their relationships to metrics programs and the use of software solutions. As part of the most recent metrics survey, 28 manufacturing metrics were identified as being the most utilized by discrete, process, and hybrid/batch manufacturers.

In their report “Guide to key performance indicators”, Price Waterhouse Coopers underlines that the main need for a company management is finding KPIs that are relevant to that particular organization, according to the industry in which it operates. For example, if a retail industry chooses Sales per square meter and Customer satisfaction as KPIs, for sure these indicators will not be useful for other business sectors, such as: banking, or oil and gas companies.

¹ R.S. Kaplan, D.P. Norton: The balanced scorecard: translating strategy into action. Harvard Business Press, Boston, 1996.

² D. Parmenter: Key performance indicators (KPI): developing, implementing, and using winning KPIs. John Wiley & Sons, New Jersey, 2010.

³ J. Hope, R. Fraser: Beyond budgeting: how managers can break free from the annual performance trap. Harvard Business Press, Boston, 2013.

⁴ PriceWaterhouseCoopers. Guide to key performance indicators — Communicating the measures that matter, 2007.

This approach is valid for robots for industrial work as well, which are used in a wide range of different manufacturing processes and face recurrent challenges towards optimization of their implementation. The main problems manufacturers face when dealing with robots are related to exploiting the best from the robot capabilities, in order to increase productivity and quality while reducing the manufacturing cost and keeping the robot system integration and reconfiguration as simple and fast as possible. Typically, there are a lot of different improvement possibilities under the robot-cells applications, the key point is to find the best process parameters that needs to be measured to provide a solution for a specific manufacturing process and product.

In more recent years, important advances have been made in technologies that allow robots to directly collaborate with humans in industrial environment. When moving from robotic cells to human-robot collaboration, the focus of the performance assessment cannot be only the robot anymore, but human factor start to play a relevant role. Different researchers^{5,6,7} have investigated the complex interactions between human and robots, analyzing which parameters have a higher influence on final HRC performances. All research highlighted the importance to provide a multifaceted approach to the problem, since final performance is affected by multiple robot factors (e.g. efficiency, cycle time, quality) and human factors (e.g. trust, situation awareness, satisfaction), all contributing to improve the job quality for operators, while increasing the manufacturing processes performances.

⁵ Steinfeld, A., Fong, T., Kaber, D., Lewis, M., Scholtz, J., Schultz, A., & Goodrich, M. *Common metrics for human-robot interaction. In Proceedings of the 1st ACM/IEEE international conference on human-robot interaction (HRI)*, Utah, USA. (2006).

⁶ Olsen, D., & Goodrich, M. *Metrics for evaluating human-robot interactions. In Proceedings of the 4th international workshop on performance metrics for intelligent systems (PERMIS)*, Maryland, USA. (2003).

⁷ Hoffman, G. *Evaluating fluency in human-robot collaboration. In Proceedings of the international conference on robotics: Science and systems (RSS)*, Berlin, Germany. (2013).

4 Global Sharework system KPIs

4.1 KPIs for industrial impact evaluation

In the first section of this deliverable, KPIs targeted to the evaluation of the performance of a manufacturing process that has implemented the Sharework system have been defined. A set of 16 main KPIs for industrial impact evaluation have been defined and is presented in detail below. This set is comprehensive of the main KPIs that are commonly used in manufacturing processes to assess the process performances, together with parameters that are more specific of human-robot collaborative systems and address the reception and acceptance of the robotic system by the human.

To achieve a multi-faceted set of KPIs, the four main drivers of Sharework have been used as a reference and each KPIs is presented, in Table 1, as addressing one or more of the four drivers.

In the table, each driver is indicated as follows:

- P: Productivity
- C: Cost
- S: Safety
- H-F: Human Factors

Table 1. KPIs correspondence to the four Sharework drivers

KPI	P	C	S	H-F
Utilization	X	X		
Efficiency	X			
Robot wait time	X			
Cycle time	X	X		
Performance	X			
Overall equipment effectiveness	X	X		
First time through	X	X		
Downtime	X	X		
Set up time	X	X		
Training hours		X		X
Unit cost		X		
Trust				X
Situation awareness			X	X
Workload	X			X
Reportable health & safety incidents			X	
Reportable environment incidents			X	

All KPIs are detailed in the sections below.

4.1.1 Utilization

Utilization measures how long a robot is being used compared to how long it could, theoretically, be used. This basic metric is relevant since all the time the robot spends without running a program is a loss of money for the company.

Utilization is defined as:

$$Utilization = \frac{Time\ Robot\ runs\ a\ program}{Total\ time}$$

The easier way to measure cobot utilization is to detect the percentage of time when it is running a program. If the robot is correctly programmed, this time will correspond to the time the robot is actually performing a task. This metric, though, does not provide indications about how well the robot is performing the task, as it only measures whether the robot is executing a task or not.

4.1.2 Efficiency

Efficiency is a relevant KPI used to determine how well robotic resources are used in the production line. Efficiency is defined as the percentage of time that the robot performs productive work while running a program. This metric provides additional information to Utilization KPI, detailing what happens while the robot is running a program.

It can be defined as:

$$Efficiency = \frac{Robot\ motion\ time}{Robot\ running\ a\ program\ time}$$

The use of the robot's motion time is a reasonable measure of a robot's Efficiency, since it is easy to measure, can be obtained directly from the robot and is a parameter available in real time. Since motion does not necessarily equal optimal productivity, it is up to the robot programmer to optimize robot motion and task execution to ensure that only the minimum motion necessary to complete the task is performed.

For this reason, efficiency is best used when coupled with other KPIs to measure robot performances. When this happens, it is an easy and reliable way to highlight a bad use of resources and improve process productivity, optimizing robot motion and better allocating it to tasks in the process to reduce waiting time.

4.1.3 Robot wait time

Wait Time is the percentage of time that the robot is waiting (i.e. not performing productive work) while it is running a program. Minimizing the robot wait time results in a direct increase of efficiency, as the two KPIs are correlated.

It is defined as the summation of all individual wait times:

$$Wait\ Time = \sum Robot\ Static\ times$$

Where Robot Static Times represents all the time the robot is running a program but it is not moving. Wait time is included inside the previous two KPIs, but it is worth measuring on its

own because, for collaborative robots, it can highlight specific processes where human and robot coordination is poorly optimized and the robot is not running at 100% of its potentiality.

4.1.4 Cycle Time

Cycle Time is a commonly used metric at several levels of manufacturing businesses, which is representative of the production line capacity to generate outputs. In the general use, Cycle Time measures how much time passes from the moment a product enters a process to the moment it exits. The KPI can then be adjusted to measure the Cycle Time of the entire manufacturing process or the Machine Cycle Time, which measures the processing time of a single machine. The former approach is more interesting to evaluate the overall performances of the manufacturing process, while the latter is relevant, particularly in robotic application, to highlight the performances of a single robot and, usually, compare it with the cycle time before robot implementation.

The Process Cycle Time can be evaluated as follows:

$$\text{Process Cycle time} = \frac{\text{Production time}}{\text{Units produced}}$$

It indicates the average time required to produce a single product, from the begin to the end of the manufacturing process.

When applied to cobots, Cycle Time is usually used as a measure of the robot task execution time. Focusing on the robot more than on the products, means that it is not relevant how many objects are produced in a certain amount of time, since multiple products could be processed in a given robot sequence.

Robot Cycle Time can be defined as:

$$\text{Cycle Time} = \text{Time sequence ends} - \text{Time sequence started}$$

In standard industrial robotic cells, cycle time could be indicated as the time passed between the beginning of the current sequence and the beginning of the previous one. In flexible collaborative human robot processes, though, the robot not always repeat the same task in the manufacturing process, making it more suited to consider a robot sequence independently and measure the time required for its completion.

A reduction in cycle time means an increase in the manufacturing process productivity, therefore its measurement should be the base for constant improvements to robot's operations to save time.

4.1.5 Performance

In standard industrial processes performed by robots, cycle time tends to be more consistent than in manual processes, since the robots guarantee higher repeatability than humans. In human-robot collaborative processes, collaboration demands higher flexibility from the robot and can result in a variation of cycle time over time. It is relevant, therefore, to measure the Performance KPI, which indicates how well the manufacturing process is performing against the planned cycle time.

Performance is defined as:

$$Performance = \frac{Actual\ cycle\ time}{Planned\ cycle\ time}$$

This metric is used to evaluate the Overall Equipment Effectiveness, described below, but it is still worth measuring on its own.

4.1.6 Overall Equipment Effectiveness

Overall equipment effectiveness (OEE) is widely used as one of the main KPIs used to analyze manufacturing processes in multiple different industries, thanks to the generic form of OEE that allows comparison between manufacturing units in differing industries. OEE is a metric that shows how manufacturing assets perform related to their theoretical maximum capacity.

OEE is computed as a combination of several measurements as follows:

$$OEE = Performance * Quality * Availability$$

Where:

- **Performance** represents the speed at which the machine runs as a percentage of its designed speed (actual cycle time / planned cycle time).
- **Quality** is the percentage of units produced without defects against the total units produced (Good units produced / Total units produced)
- **Availability** is the percentage of time that the operation is running against the total available time (Actual production time / total time).

An OEE of 100% means that only good parts are produced (100% quality), at the maximum speed (100% performance), and without interruption (100% availability).

Depending on how the total time is considered to measure Availability, different metrics are considered. In particular:

- Total Effective Equipment Performance (TEEP) considers total time to be all available time, that is 24 hours, 365 days a year.
- Overall Operations Effectiveness (OOE) considers the total operations time as the total time, meaning the maximum time a machine can potentially be operative. This includes in the count maintenance time.
- Overall Equipment Effectiveness (OEE) only considers scheduled time. If a machine is down due to maintenance, and it's not scheduled for work, OEE ignores this time.

This multi-dimensional metric can be used to indicate the overall effectiveness of robot inside a manufacturing line, both at single operation level and entire production line level. OEE measurement is therefore useful in identifying which aspects of a process can be improved and how this improvement will impact on the overall process performances.

4.1.7 First Time Through

The first-time yield (FTY) or first time through (FTT) key performance indicator is a parameter representative of both production efficiency and quality. FTT represents the number of units produced without defects and without the need for a rework against the total number of produced items in a given time period. Are considered to be defective items all those units that are not conform to the quality standards after the production process.

First Time Through can be computed as:

$$FTT = \frac{\text{Items produced with no defects}}{\text{Total items produced}}$$

Robotic applications usually increase the speed of process execution, in particular for repetitive tasks, but tend to have a lower FTT with respect to manual work. The integration of multiple cameras and sensors for online quality control during tasks execution is a way to increase FTT on robotic applications, which, in human-robot collaborative tasks, can take advantage of the operator presence as well.

4.1.8 Downtime

Process downtime is a period when the manufacturing process is on hold and no products are produced. In cobot applications it can be used to indicate, more specifically, when the robot is not working, even though the manufacturing process could still be performed manually. Downtime includes multiple scenarios, such as Idle time, maintenance or offline periods. Usually, this KPI shows a ratio of downtime to operating time and is directly related to the availability of assets for production.

Production Downtime can be computed as:

$$\text{Downtime} = \frac{\text{Robot is not used for production}}{\text{Total time}}$$

A particularly relevant part of Downtime is the Disconnected time. It is not a Key Performance Indicator, but it is an increasingly important metric for network-connected devices, which are an essential component of the Internet of Things (IoT), and a network-monitored cobot is basically functioning as an IoT device. It is essential, therefore, to minimize the amount of time the robot is disconnected from the network.

As there can be multiple different reasons for downtime, it can be beneficial to distinguish between

- Planned downtime, which is mainly referred to maintenance
- Unplanned downtime, which refers to any unforeseen event that determines a stop in robot utilization.

Downtime is a critical metric, since if, for some reason, the robot is not available, there will be a loss. While maintenance is a foreseen downtime in the life of a robot, there might be various reasons why the whole production is on stop, beginning with human factors, or mistakes, and ending with broken equipment. It is, therefore, a good practice to record the reasons for downtime and try to reduce them in the future.

4.1.9 Set up time

A key parameter strongly connected with downtime is the machine set up time. It describes the time required for a machine to adjust to changes in the production process, new products or, in case of a collaborative robot, to a shift in human personnel. Since a lot of production time can be lost to set up and changeovers, and human-robot collaboration pushes more and more towards a flexible allocation of the robotic platform, is essential to reduce set up time to the minimum.

Similarly to robot wait time, set up time is computed as the sum of all the set-up times of individual tasks:

$$\text{Set up Time} = \sum \text{Task set up time}$$

Collaborative robots are evolving, becoming comprehensive systems able to understand and interact with a changing environment, responding to external stimulus and communicating with humans through voice and gestures. This allows them to have a better understanding of the environment, resulting in a reduction of set up time for reconfiguration. Minimizing this parameter is a key step towards the optimization of robot implementation in the process.

4.1.10 Training Hourssk

Similar to the set-up time, another objective of an effective human-robot collaboration implementation is the reduction of the necessary training hours to a minimum. Keeping track of the training hours that are necessary to ensure a good mastery of the collaborative process for all operators who work in the line can help highlighting faults in the collaborative process or in the robot interfaces. If a long time is needed to train the operators, this might be the signal that some parts of the process are too complex, the robot does not provide enough information on its state or has an inconsistent behaviour when performing the same task.

Training hours can be computed as the average time required to train an operator.

4.1.11 Unit costs

This manufacturing KPI evaluates the total costs involved in the production of one item, including the fixed costs and the variable ones. This unit cost can also be broken down to show all the costs (labour, warehousing, equipment, material, etc) and analyse what are the major inputs and how much they represent in the total. In particular, for collaborative robots, the implementation in the manufacturing line can improve not only the specific task executed by the robot, but the overall process, since the implementation of the robot in some tasks can free the human for other ones.

For this reason, the analysis of the unit cost of produced items can provide a general view of the process and the impact of the introduction of the robotic system in the manufacturing line.

It is worth noting that sometimes, due to volatile energy costs for instance, unit cost has variations and cannot be measured accurately. Analysing unit cost with a trend over time, then, helps in reducing the variability caused by external factors and can highlight the evolution of a business unit costs, to visualize whether the production of a certain product is profitable.

4.1.12 Trust

Focusing more on the human side of the collaboration, rather than classical performance and economic metrics, trust has been noted as an important dimension in preserving relationships among humans and robots⁸. Due to fast paced technological advancement, the need for understanding trust in human-robot interactions is crucial to future success.

Inappropriate levels of trust that can lead to an important reduction of the robot performances in the process. Overreliance on the system can lead the operator to underestimate wrong robot behavior and fail to recognize warning signs when the automation is wrong. On the other side, a poor trust on the robot can lead the operator to limit automation performances increasing their own workload and performing unnecessarily high vigilance⁹. It becomes essential, therefore, that the level of trust between human and robot requested by the application matches the user levels.

Robot-related factors that have an impact on the user level of trust have been subcategorized, by Hancock and colleagues, into two groups: 1) robot performance-based factors and 2) robot attribute-based factors. The former, in particular, has the highest impact into the development and maintenance of users' trust. This means that improving robot performances, through the analysis of KPIs presented above, will result in an increased level of trust for the human operator when working with the robot.

Trust is often measured through self-report measures, such as questionnaires posed to the operators after collaboration with the robot. Objective measurements are proposed as well, addressing for example the physiological parameters of the user during task execution. It is important to note that individual differences between operators, such as previous experiences, age, personality, etc., influence trust level and can result in different results when working in the same automation scenario¹⁰. Also, time has an impact on the evolution of trust, since trust level can increase through time, as the operator acquire more experience working with the robot.

Trust is an important concept to consider and is at the base of a good collaboration between human and robot. It can happen, though, that the user does not trust the robot because of difficulties in understanding its state. For this reason, other KPIs, such as situation awareness, need to be evaluated.

4.1.13 Situation awareness

Situation awareness (SA) has been formally defined as the “perception of elements in the environment within a volume of time and space, the comprehension of their meaning and the projection of their status in the near future”¹¹. As it appears from the previous definition, three levels of SA are defined, namely perception (Level 1 SA), comprehension (Level 2 SA), and

⁸ Hancock, P.A., Billings, D.R., Schaefer, K.E., Chen, J.Y., De Visser, E.J., & Parasuraman, R. A Meta-Analysis of Factors Affecting Trust in Human-Robot Interaction. *Human Factors: The Journal of the Human Factors and Ergonomics Society*, 53(5), 517-527. (2011)

⁹ Parasuraman, R., & Riley, V. Humans and Automation: Use, Misuse, Disuse, Abuse. *Human Factors: The Journal of the Human Factors and Ergonomics Society*, 39(2), 230-253. (1997)

¹⁰ Bitan, Y. Meyer, J. Self-Initiated and Respondent Actions in a Simulated Control Task. *Ergonomics*, 50 (5), 763–788. (2007)

¹¹ M. Endsley, “Toward a Theory of Situation Awareness in Dynamic Systems: SituationAwareness,”*Human factors*, vol. 37, no. 1, pp. 32–64, 1995

projection (Level 3 SA). To achieve an optimal collaboration between human and robot, all three levels need to be met.

While a lot of effort is being put into the development of solutions that improve robots' awareness of and communication with humans, means to improve human understanding of the robot are less investigated. However, to have efficient human-robot interaction, SA of the human is as important as the ability of the robot to perceive and interact with the environment. A good level of SA allows the human to feel more at ease and safe, less stressed^{12,13} and also to improve his performance during task execution¹⁴.

Improving SA means to improve the information is provided to the human, both in terms of what is provided and how. This is highly related to the concept of robot transparency. Transparency is the level of information presented to the operator, which determines the comprehension about the robot's current process and future actions. Increased robot transparency has the positive effect of an empowerment of humans in the process, because it reduces the assignment of credit or blame to the robot for tasks execution. It is critical, though, to provide users with only appropriate levels of information, since higher levels of transparency do not equal higher levels of trust¹⁵. Providing too much information can overwhelm the user, while information about the system unreliability result in the user not trusting the robotic system.

Measuring SA in HRI with an industrial robot arm is not a trivial task and in literature various approaches are proposed, which are usually based on four methods: self-assessment, interview, behavioral measures and performance measures. Similarly to trust evaluation, a dedicated methodology will be developed during the Sharework project.

4.1.14 Workload

Workload can be defined as the difference between the amount of available processing resources and the amount required by a task¹⁶. Since humans have limited resources, it is important that the effort requested to the operator is of the adequate level. The term workload is used to indicate both mental workload and physical workload. The maintenance of an adequate workload for the user is essential, since both overload and underload can result in a detriment of performance. Workload overload occurs when there are too few resources available to perform the required tasks, resulting in stress and errors, while workload underload occurs when the task requires too few resources with respect to the available ones, resulting in boredom. Workload levels perceived by the users can be affected by multiple external

¹² A. M. Zanchettin, L. Bascetta, and P. Rocco, "Acceptability of Robotic Manipulators in Shared Working Environments through Human-like Redundancy Resolution," *Applied Ergonomics*, apr 2013.

¹³ . Wakita, S. Hirai, and T. Hori, "Knowledge Projection on Robot Task Environment," in *Robot and Human Communication*, 1997. RO-MAN '97. Proceedings., 6th IEEE International Workshop on, pp. 136–141, oct. 1997.

¹⁴ T. Matsumaru, "Experimental Examination in Simulated Interactive Situation between People and Mobile Robot with Preliminary-Announcement and Indication Function of Upcoming Operation," in *Robotics and Automation*, 2008. ICRA 2008. IEEE International Conference on, pp. 3487–3494, may 2008.

¹⁵ Chen, J.Y., Procci, K., Boyce, M., Wright, J., Garcia, A., & Barnes, M. Situation Awareness-Based Agent Transparency (No. ARL-TR-6905). Army Research Laboratory, Aberdeen Proving Ground, MD. Human Research and Engineering Directorate. (2014)

¹⁶ Hart, S. and Staveland, L. Development of nasa-tlx (task load index): Results of empirical and theoretical research. In Hancock, P. and Meshkati, N., editors, *Human Mental Workload*, pages 139–183. North Holland Press, Amsterdam. (1988).

factors specific to each operator, such as training, amount of skill, experience, attitude, and even external and environmental conditions.

When introducing collaborative robots in manufacturing processes, it is therefore important to well balance the amount of workload requested to the user. Aspects such as communication with the robot through voice and gestures, the use of dedicated interfaces, the reception and comprehension of information on the robot status and next actions, are additional effort that was not requested to the operator during manual manufacturing. A bad implementation of such aspects of collaboration can result in a workload overload.

Workload can be measured using a variety of subjective and objective metrics. Subjective workload metrics include self-report surveys, while objective metrics can include observational computations, measures of spare mental capacity and physiological metrics, such as heart rate, heart rate variability, and respiration rate.

The best suited strategy for the four Sharework use cases will be defined.

4.1.15 Reportable Health & Safety Incidents

This KPI is a measure of the number of health and safety incidents that were either actual incidents or near misses that were recorded as occurring over a period of time. When introducing a human-robot collaborative process in manufacturing, safety of the operator is one of the main concerns and the maximum effort should be given to reduce this value to zero.

While cobots are designed to be intrinsically safe and software modules enable the robot to perform a continuous evaluation of the operators' motion and distance to avoid collision, it is still possible for incidents to occur. Therefore, the measurement of all unplanned contacts between the human and the robot, the entity of the injuries and the number of near misses, is a relevant metric to be recorded in the manufacturing line.

Reportable health and safety incidents (RHSI) are simply measured as the sum of all undesired collisions between humans and robots plus all near misses:

$$RHSI = \sum \text{Human - robot undesired collision} + \sum \text{near misses}$$

4.1.16 Reportable Environmental Incidents

This KPI represents the same metric described above, but for incidents that caused damage to the robot or the environment. It is a measure of the number of environmental incidents that are recorded as occurring over a period of time. In this case, near misses are not considered.

Reportable Environmental Incidents (REI) is measured as the sum of all undesired collisions between the robot and the environment:

$$REI = \sum \text{Robot - environment undesired collision}$$

4.2 KPIs for modules evaluation

In this section, KPIs for module evaluation are described. The evaluation of dedicate KPIs for each module will allow to assess the performances of the Sharework system under multiple points of view, in order to ensure that all components of the system perform correctly towards the manufacturing goals.

The schematic presentation of all modules, their purpose and role, is presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Modules role and WP

Module	Modules	WPx/Tx	
Perception	#1	Knowledge base	WP2
	#2	Environment cognition	WP2
	#3	Human tracking	WP2
	#4	Primitives learning	WP2
	#5	Human task identification	WP2
Motion Planning	#6	Human-aware dynamic planning and scheduling for HRC tasks	WP3
	#7	Offline and real-time human-aware and safe robot motion planning	WP3
	#8	Robot motion planning based on learning from demonstration	WP3
HR Communication	#9	Direct and natural human-system and system-human communication	WP4
Safety and security	#10	Human safety in HRC tasks with collaborative high-payload robots	WP5
	#11	Tooling adaptation for safe HRC	WP5
	#12	Data security	WP5
Human Factors	#13	Continuous evaluation of Human ergonomics and posture correction	WP4
	#14	Operator training through AR	WP6

First, general parameters for each WP are presented and, after that, they are detailed to measure each module performance according to the respective tasks and objectives. Furthermore, for each parameter, the measurement procedure is properly described and, where it is possible, target values to be reached within the project are presented.

4.2.1 Knowledge base and workspace cognition (WP2)

This work package is divided in different modules, each of them with different goals. First of all, a robotic system knowledge base with classified and accessible information will be defined. Secondly, the workspace will be analysed to detect relevant objects and monitor motion as well as track workers. Finally, a continuous identification of human task based on real-time workspace monitoring and primitives learning will be implemented.

As there are different modules with constant interactions and most of them deal with perception, it is important to define some general parameters which will help us to understand better their performance. We will use classic metrics used in detection and classification problems.

For those modules which focus on detection, a *Ground Truth (GT) Image Set* will be created. These are the key definitions that will help us to evaluate one test:

- *True positive (TP)*: Object present in the Ground Truth and detected by the system.
- *False positive (FP)*: Object not present in the Ground Truth and detected by the system.
- *True negative (TN)*: Object not present in the Ground Truth and not detected by the system.
- *False negative (FN)*: Object present in the Ground Truth and not detected by the system.

For each test the number of all four parameters (TP, FP, TN, FN) are calculated and the following metrics can be obtained:

- *Accuracy*: It is a global measure of the system performance regarding objects that should have been detected or rejected.

$$Accuracy = (TP+TN) / GT$$

- *Precision*: It is the fraction of detected objects which are correct.

$$Precision = TP / (TP + FP)$$

- *Recall*: It is the fraction of objects that are correctly detected among all the objects that should have been detected.

$$Recall = TP / (TP + FN)$$

- *Detection Rate*: It is a measure of the percentage of objects that is detected.

$$DR = TP / (TP + FN)$$

- *False Alarm Rate*: It provides a measure of the likelihood that a detected object is correctly reported.

$$FAR = FP / (TP + FP)$$

When dealing with classification, all these parameters can be easily adapted. The input may not be only images but also other signals (e.g. primitives) and objects or actions will not be detected but classified.

Almost all the modules in the work package can use these indicators. Other metrics can be added if we consider that they give important information about the performance of the system.

Some metrics can be unused in some modules if we consider that they are not relevant for them.

It is important to remark that some of these parameters can have a slightly different interpretation in some modules. In case this happens, it will be explained.

There is another important metric which will be shared by most of the modules, that is *Computational Efficiency*. This is a crucial point in Sharework, since the system has to run in real-time, which means that all the modules need to run in a feasible frequency. All the module parameters will have to adapt to reach a compromise between quality performance and time efficiency.

4.2.1.1 Knowledge Base

This module aim is to design and develop a Knowledge Base (KB) capable of supporting all the cognitive processes involved in the Sharework control system by leveraging and extending a suited ontology such as, e.g., IEEE 1872-2015 “Standard Ontologies for Robotics and Automation”. Such a KB would characterize all the information needed to interpret human instructions/commands, interpret the status of the work-cell and the status of the human operators, recognize production processes and automatically generate collaborative tasks accordingly. Moreover, the module is to realize a set of knowledge processing mechanisms capable of dynamically infer new knowledge, guarantying the continuous update of the KB over time. In this way, the control system will always have an updated control model.

In order to evaluate the performance and, also, the effectiveness of the module, two different perspectives will be considered:

- *Modeling perspective*: the KB will be designed upon a dedicated ontology (specifically defined for Sharework) capable of representing all the use cases of the pilots as well as all the relevant human-robot collaboration aspects of the modeled processes. Under this terms, the module will influence all the parameters reflecting the representational capabilities such as, e.g., accuracy, precision, recall, etc.
- *Reasoning perspective*: a set of knowledge processing mechanisms must maintain correctness and validity of the KB over time. The main KPI of the inference processes is related to Efficiency and must be comparable with the latencies of the production environment.

4.2.1.2 Environment Cognition

In this module a general semantic cognition method will be developed, which enables the vision network to detect certain objects and classify them using a unique identifier. For classification, machine learning approaches will be used. These algorithms have to be taught on the specific use case in order to achieve a satisfactory level of confidence. Therefore, this module requires training data from the different use case owners.

The vision system will be set up in such a way, that the field of vision is blocked as less as possible. In order to allow a certain level of reliability and redundancy the system is projected to cover the desired objects with at least two different sensors. This module has high requirements regarding resolution and accuracy of the classified and segmented objects, as these are used in high-level tasks.

Further the module will provide following outputs:

- Segmented and classified point clouds;
- If required, geometrical or voxelized hulls of static objects and room features;
- If required, all objects can further be flagged as static or dynamic;
- All data can be forwarded to the knowledge base.

This is based on following input data:

- 3D-camera network providing individual point cloud scans;
- Absolute pose of the sensors according to a general reference frame.

Different indicators have been defined to examine this module:

- *Accuracy*: in this module, accuracy means the resolution and error-properties of the segmented scans. The vision system needs to provide such a high accuracy that all tasks (e.g. silicone appliance, riveting) can be fulfilled. The required accuracy is dependent on the used sensors, the design and error-tolerance in the tool, the process tolerances, etc.;
- *Reliability*: reliability is defined as the ability to classify objects correctly. The aim is to achieve state-of-the-art reliability, which is 60-80% for vision classification, depending on the used algorithms and sources (we aim for the upper end);
- *Computational Efficiency*: it is very unlikely to achieve real-time computation if we want to detect a great number of objects with a huge number of sensors, given the amount of scan data to process. It is for this reason that the module will have to find a compromise between performance and efficiency.

4.2.1.3 Human Tracking

Human tracking is the process of locating humans over time using one or multiple cameras. To perform this tracking this module will analyse sequential video frames and create a trajectory. This means that we can divide the whole process in two basic steps: detection and location in one frame, and tracking using information from all frames. As a result, performance indicators in this module will be divided in two steps:

4.2.1.3.1 Frame-based metrics

The frame-based metrics will be used to evaluate the human detection performance on individual frames. A Ground Truth Image Set containing humans will be created. This set will have to be general and robust enough, which implies that different environments, actions, lighting conditions, occlusions will be taken into account when defining the set. Moreover, frames without any human will be added to the set. For each frame human positions will be labelled.

All the metrics defined at the introduction of the work package will be used.

- *Accuracy*;
- *Precision*;
- *Recall*;
- *Detection Rate*;
- *False Alarm Rate*;
- *Computational Efficiency*.

4.2.1.3.2 Tracking-based metrics

The tracking-based metrics measure the ability to track humans over time. As in the previous case, a Ground Truth Video Set containing humans moving in videos will be created. Moreover, this set will also have to be general and robust enough. For each frame from each video human positions will be labelled, so that a complete track is obtained. Most of the general metrics will be used to measure the performance of the module.

At this point, apart from general metrics, there is another point of view which is important to consider, i.e. how well the tracker estimates the exact positions of the human along all the video. That means how different is a correctly detected track from what we expected. Therefore, there is the need of another set of important metrics which focus on the quality of the tracking. It is important to remark that these indicators will measure the quality of a single track so statistical analysis of all samples will have to be done to have a general view.

- *Track Matching Error*: it measures error between the obtained track and its corresponding one at the Ground Truth Set by calculating the average distance error in all frames;
- *Track Completeness*: it is defined as the time the obtained track overlaps with the Ground Truth Set track divided by the total duration of the track;
- *Track Detection Latency*: it is the time delay of the obtained track start compared to the Ground Truth Set track start.

All these KPIs have been thought to be analysed using only images, i.e. 2D detection and tracking. However, if human 3D information is available in GT set (for example using extra sensors to obtain this information), all metrics can be used in the same way to measure the performance of the system not only in images but in 3D.

It is also important to remark that both frame-based and tracking-based metrics can be applied to specific parts of the human skeleton that will be detected. For example, if it is considered that it is relevant to the project having the information of the hand, the same analysis can be done.

We have defined many indicators and it is difficult to define a target for all of them. However, we will focus on accuracy and computational efficiency. Accuracy in our dataset (from different use cases) must be higher than current accuracy of the state-of-the-art algorithms in general datasets (60-80%), so 90% of accuracy should be reached. Moreover, the system should be able to process more than 20 frames per second to ensure a real time solution. This implies that image resolutions will be adapted, if necessary, to fit time requirements.

4.2.1.4 Primitives Learning

Motion primitives learning module takes as input the human tracking trajectories and object segmentation and translate them into useful features for both human task identification and safe motion planning modules. In particular, the motion primitives learning algorithm segments the trajectories with a semantic understanding and build motion primitives that represent these segments. Later, these learned primitives can be applied to predict complete human trajectories from partially observed trajectories.

The metrics of the segmentation and motion primitives building cannot be evaluated independently as this module interacts constantly with Human Task Identification module and different modules in Task and motion planning for HR cooperation work package. It is for these reason that at this moment it is very difficult to define specific indicators. As the project moves on, once we have the relations between modules more defined, it will be possible to set some indicators.

4.2.1.5 Human Task Identification

Human Task identification is the process of identifying what a human is doing. The input of this module will be the primitives obtained in the previous one, which means that, to evaluate the performance of this module, we will work only with validated primitives. We will not consider inputs with errors as we want to evaluate the module separately. In case we wanted to use this module to analyse primitives learning performance, all inputs should be considered.

The key definitions explained before are also valid for this module and most of the metrics will be used to measure its performance. Moreover, the number of actions to identify is an important metric to evaluate as the rest of indicators will depend on this parameter.

- *Number of actions;*
- *Accuracy;*
- *Precision;*
- *Recall;*
- *Detection Rate;*
- *False Alarm Rate.*

As in the human tracking module, we have defined many indicators and it is difficult to define a target for all of them. We will focus on number of actions detected and accuracy. More than 15 different actions should be identified and accuracy in our dataset (from different use cases) must be higher than 80% identifying different actions defined in Sharework.

4.2.2 Task and motion planning for HR cooperation (WP3)

WP3 aims at developing an integrated robot motion planner and task planner that are able to take into account human safety and comfort as well as granting system productivity. Three software modules are with WP3: task planning and scheduling module (#6), the safe robot motion planning module (#7) and learning by demonstration module (#8).

As described in the DoW, the functional the task planning and scheduling module (Module#6) will select the best task for the robot among the robot tasks available. Moreover, if existing, the most suitable trajectory is identified among a set of predefined trajectories. Under the direct request of support from the worker, the module selects the best robot trajectories. The set of trajectories, off-line computed by the safe robot motion planning module (Module#7), present differences in terms of the expected interaction with the human (e.g. speed, acceleration, path, distance from the worker, execution time). Robot trajectories can also be calculated in real-time or, alternatively, evaluated exploiting learning from demonstration (#8) on the basis of human gesture.

The three modules, therefore, cover three different aspects related to the motion planning: the selection of task & trajectory given the identification of the human actions and context; the calculus and adaptation of the trajectories; and finally, the natural teaching of new trajectories/behaviors to the robot.

Because of the different goals associated with the different modules, the KPIs are specifically related to each module, and no general glossary and common definitions are therefore necessary.

4.2.2.1 Human Aware dynamic planning and scheduling for HRC Tasks

The general goal of the human aware dynamic planning and scheduling module (#6) is to develop a dynamic task planning system which is both human and context aware hence able to both reason on the user model and interpret a number of sensorial information by connection with other modules of the system (modules #1-5). In this regard, the task planning system is responsible for continuously creating and keep updated a collaborative plan for the robot adapted to the actual operative context.

In developing the some qualitative KPI concerning efficiency will be considered, i.e., improvement of productivity (20%), quality / throughput increase (15%), reduction of robot idle time / increase of robot speed (20%) and resources optimization. Moreover, the module will contribute in improving the ability of the overall system to guarantee human safety. Specifically, the dynamic task planning system will generate robot task sequence that prevent collisions and reduce risks (performance related to integration with module #7).

Finally, operator satisfaction is a key aspect to consider and, then, task plans will be generated to foster natural human-robot collaborations, a positive user experience. More in general, the above features are to favour technology acceptance from human operators and facilitate the deployment of the new Sharework technology.

The probabilistic reasoning sub-module will use some of the pieces of information saved in the Knowledge Base about the actual status of the system (the inputs) to derive decision values and predictions (the outputs) that will be used as triggers for the main planner.

Furthermore, the parallel planning feature with its according smoothing algorithms will ensure at each time step that a valid plan is available for the actors.

- Probabilistic reasoning: Generate decision values with a correct rate greater than x% and predictions with a correct rate greater than x%. The correctness of the decision values and of the predictions is determined by a human. Afterwards the correct rates are computed as the ratio between the decision values (and predictions) that were correctly determined by the algorithm and the total number of decision values (and predictions).
- Parallel planning feature: Reduce the idle time of the robot due to re-planning procedures by x%. Compute the idle time that occurs due to re-planning when re-planning is triggered at the same time points and under the same conditions over a set of test plans, with and without the parallel planning feature, and compute the relative reduction in time.

4.2.2.2 Offline and real-time human aware and safe robot motion planning

In module #7, the goal is the design of innovative methodologies for online and offline motion planning, dealing with complex application scenarios where human is a non-controllable resource.

Therefore, the key performance indexes (KPIs) of the module are related to the increase of easiness for the operator in using the robot, the increase of productivity for the working cell and the improvement of the ergonomics and acceptance of the robot by the human operator. Specifically, the metrics to evaluate the success of the planning module are at the writing phase the following:

1. Improvement of the State of the art in motion planning in a complex industrial scenario:
 - *Challenge*: Reduction of 20% for the calculus for a collision free trajectory in a shared workspace, with a large number of obstacles;
 - *Baseline*: the baseline for the calculus of the improvement will be the usage of the best performing trajectory generator (at the D1.6 writing time the most performing methodologies are BiTRRT / STOMP / TrjOpt).
2. Improvement of the easiness in programming the robot cell, i.e., indirect cost reduction:
 - *Challenge*: Reduction of 80% for programming time.
 - *Baseline*: a set of at least ten different trajectories have to be calculated using industrial best-practice
3. Improvement of work- cell productivity, i.e., direct cost reduction:
 - *Challenge*: Reduction of 20% of robot stop/hold during the trajectory execution because of a human safety risk, i.e., ability to modify the trajectory to avoid risk to the human in the 20% of the cluttered applications;
 - *Baseline*: a set of experiments where the human-robot collaboration foreseen not-synchronized applications, and therefore, possible stops due to the human presence in robot proximity may happen. The baseline, therefore, will be created just using the Speed and Separation Monitoring as described in the standard 10218/b-TS15666.
4. Improvement of the human acceptance of the robots, i.e., human factors:
 - *Challenge*: Increase of the 25% the dependability evaluation from the user;
 - *Baseline*: an evaluation based on the adoption of questionnaires that compare the movement generated by the best-practice industrial application with the output of the motion planned.

4.2.2.3 Robot Motion Planning based on learning from demonstration

Learning from Demonstration is an alternative tool for motion planning on which the human teaches to the robot, generally through manual guidance, the correct path to follow in each different task. Indeed, the robot learns these motions and imitates them, trying to adapt and generalize them over the taught examples.

The Learning from Demonstration module can be indirectly studied in terms of Human factor, since it affects many aspects of them, namely:

- *Safety*: LfD, as an alternative to motion planning, has to ensure operator safety during operations, e.g. avoiding collision;
- *Operator acceptance*: as LfD foresees a close cooperation between the human and the robot during the teaching, acceptance is essential to guarantee a successful training of the robot;

Human-system communication: a simple and natural communication between the operator and the robot is necessary to speed up the learning process of motions through different tasks.

At the same time, LfD module could be evaluated also in terms of cost and productivity, since smooth and fast motions allow to decrease cycle time.

4.2.3 HR Interfaces for effective collaboration (WP4)

A communication system able to allow direct and natural exchange of information between the human and the system will be studied and implemented within this WP. Applications for AR and algorithms for gesture recognition will be developed. Moreover, a methodology to assess ergonomics in human-robot collaborative workplaces will be developed. The tool that evaluates ergonomics in real time, proposes ergonomically correct postures and interacts with the system in order to optimize the robot configuration for improving human ergonomics will be implemented. These developments are packaged as two separate modules, a) Module 9: Direct and natural human-system and system-human communication and b) Module 13: Continuous evaluation of Human ergonomics and posture correction. The key performance indicators for each are presented separately due to their innate qualities in the approach and implementation. In particular section 4.2.3.1 presents the initial factors for Module 9 evaluation and section 4.2.5.1 for Module 13.

4.2.3.1 Direct and natural human-system and system-human communication

This module is designed to provide smart solutions for enhancing the interaction of human operators with the rest Sharework's system. Augmented reality application running on headset devices and smart screen applications for tablet are some of the designed approaches for publishing information to the workers. In terms of process evaluation one metric that can depict the performance of the developed applications is the cycle time with and without the human operator assistant tools. The evaluation of this module is mostly depended on human factors. The following major categories have been identified for the systematic evaluation of usability of AR systems.

- *Interaction with the system:* refers to the mechanisms that allow the user to interact with the system (markers, audio, mouse, unconventional devices);
- *Application Interface:* is related to issues, such as interface /system. It is presented to the user in terms of ease of use and learning, flexibility of use, among others;
- *Representation:* relates to aspects perceived by the user, such as the appearance that the interface presents to the user;
- *Sensory and Behavioural Aspects:* are related to how the interface can be intuitive, promote user adaptation, in addition to immersion;
- *Motivation and Effort:* relates to how the system can hold the user's attention, motivating him to use and reuse the application;
- *Spatial Association:* refers to the distribution in space of the virtual and real environment, overlapping them. Therefore, the virtual objects inserted onto the scene should have proportional sizes to the real environment;
- *Internal and Configuration aspects:* refers to aspects that allow the application to be ready for use.

All these categories are planned to be validated based on surveys that will take place with human workers.

4.2.3.2 Continuous evaluation of Human ergonomics and posture correction

The continuous and dynamic real-time assessment would be influenced by Module #3 and module #5. The input from these modules would be needed to detect the data of joint angles and human pose for classifying the quality of the human postures.

The results of this ergonomic assessment should be proceeded in Module #9 to give the worker feedback for their ergonomic state and guiding them how to better this.

To evaluate the ergonomic state of the current work there would be implemented a questionnaire for an initial analysis, called AWS light. The result of this rough method is an overview about handled loadings and strained body regions. Regarding the developed of a dynamic ergonomic assessment this KPI could be used to assess the further HRC-workplace. With the development of a dynamic and continuous ergonomic assessment the possibility for a new KPI arises, which is not comparable with the current state.

4.2.4 System flexibility through human safety and reliable and secure computing architectures (WP5)

In general, this WP would be influenced by module # 10 (human safety in HRC tasks with collaborative and high payload-robots), module # 11 (tooling adoption for safe HRC) and module #12 (data security).

4.2.4.1 Human safety in HRC tasks with collaborative and high-payload robots

The relevant parameters for a safe collaboration are:

- System flexibility by dynamic zone-model, with respect to the Robot;
- Dynamic sensor management for redundant data processing with dynamic zones and level of interaction (HRC-level by IWU);
- Dynamic risk assessment with system stops while individual breaks security lines or danger zones;
- Safe computing architecture by using FPGA for deterministic Robot Real-time communication with period of 8ms.

The quality of this parameters could be measured with process KPIs (e.g. time saving per task) in an economic way.

For evaluating the safety of this parameters there already existing no KPIs, because current methods can only compare initial situations and further solutions by using conventional safety sensors (e.g. Safety Integrity Level or Performance Level).

4.2.4.2 Tooling Sensors adaption for safe HRC

Module 11 is closely correlated to the KPIs of Module 2 regarding complexity and computation times. The same indicators Accuracy, Reliability and Computational Efficiency as described in 4.2.1.2 Environment cognition will be used.

Further on, by adapting the safety system on the TCP, the system is projected to improve behaviour while being subject to occlusion. This enables the generation of more reliable safety

zones. For the generation of the safety zones no other specific KPIs than those mentioned above will be defined as the quality of the safety zones highly depends on how the output of this module will be further processed.

4.2.4.3 Data security

The Data Security module will develop a specific security policy and prescribe policies for the communications and operations management, as well as access control policies to fortify the overall information security of the system. These policies will be the result of a dedicated and diligent analysis of the involved systems.

The aim of the aforementioned policies will be to mitigate the identified potential threats related to privacy, identity and integrity in order to provide an adequate level of security.

Effectively the developed data security module will be a toolset. This toolset will provide both data security Policies and Practices as well as a list of software libraries and tools that will aim to increase the data security of the software systems. The toolset will be generic and potentially applicable to all use cases and modules. Use case developers and module developers will be able to select and apply tools and policies to fortify the data security where needed.

Usual Data security KPIs tend to quantify the security incidents and the effects of security incidents. Some common Data Security KPIs are provided below for completeness.

- Number of Reported Incidents;
- Number of Major Security Incidents;
- Number of Small Security Incidents;
- Cost Per Incident;
- Amount of Time to Resolve an Incident;
- Downtime During an Incident.

In order to be applicable these KPIs require installations that are open to data security incidents in real operating environments. This particular condition is not normally available during prototypes development and is not expected to be applicable during the project. Therefore, measuring the aforementioned data Security KPIs will not be practical or meaningful in the SHAREWORK project.

However, a practical measure of the application of the policy would be to quantify the number of security standards, tools and policies implemented and available to use for each use case

4.2.5 Human factor analysis and technology acceptance (WP6)

Because Human-Robot Collaboration acceptance is one of the main objectives of the project, it is the subject of a specific work package, with its own KPIs. The Human Factors analysis will be built upon two main pillars, namely collaborative governance and collective intelligence. It has started from the very beginning of the Project, so that when the training and integration phase comes, it can benefit from a favourable mindset.

Trust in the technology is a key component of technology acceptance, and will be assessed accordingly, as developed in section 4.1.12.

Technology acceptance as such will be evaluated through different methodologies: standard surveys (e.g. European Working Condition Survey) and specific questionnaires, in order to

capture the shared attitudes toward the cobot in the facilities; individual interviews with the operators and the management before and after the integration of the cobots; focus groups to identify and act upon remaining pain points.

4.2.5.1 Operator training through AR

In general, this module concerns the same aspects described in section 4.2.3.1 "*Direct and natural human-system and system-human communication*". Therefore, the same major categories for the evaluation of the usability of the AR system have been identified and briefly reported below.

- *Interaction with the system;*
- *Application Interface;*
- *Representation;*
- *Sensory and Behavioural Aspects;*
- *Motivation and Effort;*
- *Spatial Association;*
- *Internal and Configuration aspects.*

Regarding the operator training through AR specifically, two metrics will be used to evaluate its performance: on the one hand the time required by an operator to adapt to changes in the task processes; on the other hand the time required to introduce the workflow to a new operator, in comparison with the same task without the cobot. The evaluation of the gesture recognition algorithm, which will be implemented within this module, is closely linked with the human tracking module #3. The aforementioned KPIs in section 4.3.1.3 are also suitable for assessing the performance of this module.

4.3 Conclusions

D1.6 presented a comprehensive set of performance indicators for the Sharework system. In particular, performance metrics and methodologies for the assessment of the system industrial impact and the performance of each module have been presented and detailed. The objective of the deliverable, which is the definition of performance metrics for the evaluation of the Sharework system as implemented in a general manufacturing process, has been achieved and details have been provided for the evaluation of all main features of the Sharework system.

The system development is currently in its initial stage and the information provided in D1.6 is referred to standard state of the art techniques for assessment of each modules and to industrial practices for process performance evaluation. As the technological development of all modules will proceed, more knowledge will be produced on the connection and collaboration between modules and on the implementation details in the four use cases of the Sharework project. This knowledge will allow to further improve the information provided in this report and will be included in D1.7, that will deal with the definition of more specific KPIs for all four use cases.